

A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL OF DATA-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING IN PRIVATE SECONDARY HIGH SCHOOLS IN REGION XI

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ABSTRACT

The data-driven decision-making in school is misinterpreted, and malpractice by educators' policy makers. The implementation of data-driven decision-making encountered problems such as intent on its practice oftentimes be confusing or extremely misused leading to misconception and wrong implementation. This quantitative study utilized descriptive correlational approach to test the validity of a multi-variate model that best fits in predicting the data-driven decision making among school leaders using structural equation modeling. This study selected school leaders from private secondary schools in Region XI using proportional stratified random sampling. The result showed a high level of school leaders' transformational leadership, knowledge management, data use, and data driven decision making. The effectiveness of data utilization in academic institutions was significantly influenced by the collated impact of knowledge management systems and transformational leadership. The best fit model inferred that these two variables must operate in tandem to bolster data-driven decision-making of the school leader. The structural relationship observed between data use, knowledge management system, and transformational leadership emphasized the underlying role these factors play in enabling academic institutions to implement effective data-driven decision-making.

Keyword: - Education, transformational leadership, knowledge management, data use, data driven decision making, school leaders, school principal, descriptive correlational, Philippines

1. INTRODUCTION

Turnover iData-driven decision-making is an academic and professional practice that considers analysis of wide range confounding factors of data to come up with a reasonable decision rather than depending on purely intuition (Provost, , & Fawcett, 2023). In the realm of academic institutions, data-driven decision-making is often associated as a formative worldview as strong organizational culture of DDDM promotes effective use of relevant and diagnostic data to inform almost seamless transformational, instructional and operational decisions (Brynjolfsson & McElheran, 2022; Avci, 2020). The data-driven decision-making in school was misinterpreted, and malpracticed by educators policy makers. In the global perspective, a finding from the study of Johnson and Christensen (2021), in United States of America, noted a misconception on data-driven decision-making and this rate tripled by eleven percent to thirty percent in a span of five years. worldwide evolving implementation of data-driven decision-making

encountered problems such as intent on its practice can often times be confusing or extremely misused leading to misconception about data-driven decision-making.

Further, a study Harris et. al. (2020), as the school leaders experienced confusion on the implementation of data-driven decision-making in more than four years as information overload and decision paralysis triggered by grappling large amount of overwhelming data from diverse and different sources. On central and south pacific, particularly in Australia, there was a challenge on the malpractice in data-driven decision-making leading to decision paralysis and lack of knowledge management may lead to a stagnant professional or academic growth, unproductive organizational milieu, and worst, institutional bankruptcy (Gaviria-Rivera, J. I., & López -Zapata, 2019; Harris et. al., 2020).

Additionally, a study conducted by Akkaya et. Al (2020) across seven countries in Europe, Austria, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Spain, Germany and Sweden, the research result shows noticeable downgrade on the implementation of data-driven decision-making brought by the integration of transformation processes of technology that hindered optimization of processes and outputs in academe. In Africa, a study shows the research attention has also been drawn to growing three percent rate on the number of protests caused unethical data-driven decision-making of the school leaders (Al-Mahdy, Emam,& Hallinger, 2019). The above-mentioned situations revealed strong evidences that the concern of data-driven decision making is a worldwide phenomenon.

A recent data based in the Philippines, data-driven decision-making is poorly practiced in public school context presented by Gaviria-Rivea et. al. (2019). Despite of the available resource data from various sources such as National Achievement Test (NAT), the data driven decision making in the Philippines is poorly practiced as shown from the selected public secondary schools among principals and among teacher in the Philippines leading to wrong implementation of curriculum. To support the claim, the study of Bringula (2022) conducted in Metro Manila have shown despite the numerous number of data available, the school leaders, if not poorly practicing the data-driven decision-making, tend to commit incorrect data use on the data interpretation or flawed decision-making processes that have led to detrimental negative effects on student outcome such decreased academic achievement, discouragement, and worst, dropout.

On a local scale in the island of Mindanao, specifically in Zamboanga peninsula, successful data-driven decision-making practice secure finance and longevity plan in the private education sector supported by data-driven decision making initiatives. On the contrary, school leaders where identified with deficiencies in knowledge management in data-driven decision-making have impeded ineffective data utilization by investing to non-urgent factors on school development (Marenee et al, 2022) On a closer perspective, in Davao Region, specifically in Digos City, Davao del Sur, principal or school heads from different private institutions have made the initiative in seminars for appropriate practice of data-driven decision-making for the mid-admin and teachers, it has shown on an evaluation that there is a correlation of less exposure to data-driven decision-making related seminar to impractical decision such as investment of irrelevant projects and infrastructures.

In Davao City, as a result of the recent years' trying times, a tertiary educational institutions have experienced data quality issues as there were roll out of centralized data system with incomplete and inaccurate information as this leads to faulty data-driven decision-making resource allocation. On top of it, school leaders have experienced teacher resistance as these educators have limited understanding of data driven decision making beyond numbers (Junsay., 2016; Bentilan et. al, 2023).

Among the numerous various variables filtered by the researcher through readings, the following stood out for the relevance and recency: transformational leadership is highly correlated to data-driven decision making, data use is positively correlated to data-driven decision making, and knowledge management system is correlated to data-driven decision making.

The researcher identified from the literature that the following variables were being examined in connection with data-driven decision-making; thus, a number of studies about data-driven decision-making is also linked to various variables. A number of research shows that data-driven decision-making (DDDM) paired with the level of data use. As it highlights the effect of data-driven decision-making techniques which are essential for improving data use for Industry maintenance applications, according to research. By using these techniques, companies can make well-informed decisions, optimize maintenance plans, and effectively analyze large datasets (Bousdekis, 2021; Ruschel, 2017).

Significant limitation on oversimplifying complex interrelationships among aforementioned variables are highlighted on the several literature and researches accessed by the researcher. It was noted that the bivariate analyses have been used extensively in prior research on data-driven decision-making (DDDM), with an emphasis on distinct correlations between variables (Bousdekis, 2021; Ruschel, 2017; Brynjolfsson, Hitt, & Kim, 2021). Hence, research using multivariate models that look at the combined and interrelated effects of knowledge management systems, data utilization, and transformational leadership on DDDM results needs to be explored especially when it comes to private

secondary high schools. Secondly, majority of current research on data-driven decision-making (DDDM) is focused mostly on business or industrial settings, prioritizing operational effectiveness and financial gain over learning objectives (Courtney, 2021; Christenson & Goldstein, 2022; Schildkamp, 2019).

Further, the immediate relevance of these circumstances to the education sector, especially in private secondary schools, is still not well understood, despite the fact that they provide insightful information. Research on the ways in which knowledge management systems, data utilization, and transformational leadership interact to influence DDDM practices in schools is particularly lacking. The absence of contextualization is even more noticeable in Region XI, where distinct organizational and sociocultural elements can affect how these variables function. To adapt DDDM frameworks to the unique requirements and difficulties faced by educational institutions in this area, it is imperative that this gap be filled (Wayman, 2017; Grissom et al., 2021; Cole-Foppe, 2016). Lastly, the underexplored interrelationship among variables. The intricate links between transformative leadership, data utilization, and knowledge management systems—all of which have been recognized as significant determinants of DDDM may be researched but rarely examined in the literature. A thorough grasp of the causal pathways and mechanisms by which these variables interact to improve DDDM in educational contexts is hampered by this gap (Christenson & Goldstein, 2022). The current study is a multivariate utilizing structural equation model.

The researcher disseminated the findings of the study through school trainings for school leaders within the region and beyond. Moreover, the researcher communicated the findings of the study to a wider audience through a wider scope of listeners and researchers such as local and international research forum, research congress, research summit and relative research conferences. The researcher submitted to the manuscript to officially publish the research in appropriate research journal or publication in high-indexed international journals.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research approach particularly descriptive correlational design. A quantitative research approach refers to the collection and statistical analysis of numerical data to test hypotheses, discuss and describe an phenomena, and examine relationships among variables (Creswell, 2014; Leedy & Ormrod, 2019). It is grounded in positivist philosophy, which assumes that reality can be objectively measured and quantified (Babbie, 2020); Muijs, 2011). Quantitative research is best perfect for a research study that involves large sample sized and requires a general scope of findings.

In the context of this study, the descriptive correlational research design was chosen because it aligned well with the study's objectives. The objective is to examine and discuss existing conditions related to data-driven decision making among school leaders and identify potential associations between variables without manipulating them. Since the study was conducted on an academic educational setting, an experimental or causal-comparative design was not appropriate. Perhaps, descriptive correlational research provided a practical and ethical way to collect and analyze data while preserving the integrity of the educational settings and its conditions. This design also allowed for the use of statistical tools to assess relationships and generate findings that can inform policy and teacher development programs. As supported by the literature, this kind of research approach is commonly employed in social and educational research to explore phenomena where variables should not be controlled or manipulate (Pilot & Beck, 2021; Cohen et. al, 2018; Muijs, 2011).

The respondents of this study were the school administrators from private secondary schools in region XI. There were 300 randomly chosen respondents. Sample size was calculated using the Raosoft sample size calculator (Raosoft Inc, 2004) with 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. Proportional stratified random sampling is the sampling technique used. With this method, the population is separated into geographically based strata, and a proportionate sample is taken from each stratum to represent the true distribution of school administrators. The identified school administrators was assigned numbers, and participants was chosen at random from each stratum using a random number generator. Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) provide support for this approach, emphasizing how it can improve the generalizability of quantitative results while maintaining the integrity of population representation.

The distribution of target respondents by strata is as follows: There were 96 responders, or roughly 596 to 1,490 administrators from 149 schools in Davao City (32 percent). 39 responders, including 244–610 administrators, which came from 61 schools in Davao del Sur (13 percent). 33 responders, comprising 204 to 510 administrators, comes from 51 schools in Davao de Oro (11 percent). 51 responders comes from 79 Davao del Norte schools (17%) with 316–790 administrators. 54 responders comes from 84 Davao Oriental schools (18%) with between 336 and 840 administrators. Davao Occidental (9%), which consists of 42 schools with 168–420 administrators, which have 27 responders. The accuracy and robustness are enhanced by the 300 respondents' overall proportionate representation across all divisions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based from the analyzed data, The correlation between Transformational Leadership (TL) and Knowledge Management System (KMS) was positive and significant ($r = 0.338$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that levels of transformational leadership are associated with successful knowledge management practice implementation. This is in support of García-Morales, Jiménez-Barrionuevo, and Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez's (2012) postulation, which emphasized that transformational leaders enable organizational learning and knowledge sharing. The relationship between knowledge management system (KMS) and Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM) was positive and moderate in significance ($r = .450$, $p < 0.05$), showing that the successful application of KMS facilitates better data-driven decision-making processes directly. The improvement of the KMS would also improve the DDDM. This is supported by Provost & Fawcett (2023) research that well-established knowledge systems significantly improve organizational decision-making quality. The relationship between Data Use (DU) and Transformational Leadership (TL) was statistically weaker ($r = .177$, $p < 0.05$) but positive, which indicates the limited influence of leadership on the degree of data use. This concurs with the study by Darling-Hammond et al. (2022), who discovered that while transformational leaders develop a data use culture, their effect is indirect and mediated by other influences within an organization.

Table 1

Significance of Relationship of Transformational Leadership, Knowledge Management System, and Data Use to Data-Driven Decision Making

<i>Variables Paired</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>Transformational Leadership (TL) vs. Knowledge Management System (KMS)</i>	.338	.000	<i>Significant</i>
<i>Knowledge Management System (KMS) vs. Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM)</i>	.450	.000	<i>Significant</i>
<i>Transformational Leadership (TL) vs. Data Use (DU)</i>	.177	.000	<i>Significant</i>

The Figure 1 illustrates the hypothesized measurement model of the study. It comprises four key latent variables: Transformational Leadership (TL), Knowledge Management System Life Cycle (KMSLC), Data Use (DU), and Data-Driven Decision-Making (DDDM). TL is conceptualized based on five dimensions: Idealized Influence (Attitude and Behavior), Inspirational Motivation (IM), Intellectual Stimulation (IS), and Individualized Consideration (IC). KMSLC is represented through six constructs: Create Knowledge (CK), Capture Knowledge (CA), Refine Knowledge (RK), Store Knowledge (SK), Manage Knowledge (MK), and Disseminate Knowledge (DK). DU includes variables related to user characteristics, data use culture, system characteristics, and more, while DDDM is measured through Technological Infrastructure and Hardware (TIH), Data Usage Culture (DUC), Data Use Purpose (DUP), and Data Literacy (DL).

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model of the Study

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). CFA was conducted to evaluate the measurement model. Figure 1 shows that the factor loadings for TL indicators ranged from 0.58 to 0.80, all exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.50, indicating good convergent validity. The KMSLC dimensions loaded well on the latent construct, though some indicators showed marginal values (e.g., RK with -0.25), suggesting possible issues in model fit. DU indicators had strong loadings ranging from 0.48 to 0.78. The measurement model also reflects high internal consistency, with indicators such as UC (0.72), SOC (0.52), and DUSD (0.78) contributing significantly to the latent construct.

Goodness of Fit of the Hypothesized Model. Table 2 details the required criterion values for model goodness-of-fit. The analysis indicates that Model 1 stands as the most suitable fit because its criteria match those required for a good model fit. The model fit can be considered satisfactory because CMIN/DF stands at 1.357 below the essential threshold value of 3. The NFI (Normed Fit Index) stands at 0.912 meeting and surpassing the recommended standard value of 0.90. The TLI score surpasses 0.90 at 0.971 and the CFI results reach 0.975 above 0.90. The assessment of model fit through measuring the GFI shows excellent results because it surpasses the recommended threshold at 0.931.

Table 2
Goodness of Fit Measures of the Best Fit Model

Indices	Criteria	Model 1
CMIN/DF	<3.0	1.357
NFI	>.90	0.912
TLI	>.90	0.971
CFI	>.90	0.975
GFI	>.90	0.931
RMSEA	<.08	0.035
PCLOSE	>.05	0.991

To address the lack of fit, a model-generating technique was employed, using the modification indices provided by AMOS. As recommended by Creswell (2024), data-driven re-specification of SEM models can be applied to improve model fit when theory supports plausible adjustments.

The resulting best-fit model is presented in Figure 2. After modifying paths and removing low-loading indicators, model fit improved substantially. The revised model retained the core latent constructs but altered structural paths and measurement indicators to enhance parsimony and fit. Key changes included strengthening the mediating role of DU and adjusting the paths between KMSLC and DDDM. The final model reflects a well-fitting structure for understanding DDDM in schools. Transformational Leadership exerts a dual influence—both directly on DDDM and

indirectly via DU and KMSLC. DU emerged as a powerful mediator, particularly in linking leadership behaviors with actionable data-driven practices. The minimal influence of KMSLC on DDDM ($\beta = 0.11$) in the revised model suggests that while knowledge systems are foundational, their impact is contingent on user engagement and leadership.

Figure 2
The Best Fit Model

Legend: PLS= Principal Leadership Style; TM= Teacher Motivation; JS= Job Satisfaction; TI= Turnover Intention; PLSDS_m= Principal Leadership Style Directive Style; PLSPS_m= Principal Leadership Style Participative Style; PLSS_m= Principal Leadership Style Supportive; PLSA_m= Principal Leadership Style Achievement-oriented; TMIM_m= Teacher Motivation Intrinsic Motivation; TMEM_m= Teacher Motivation Extrinsic Motivation; comm_m= Communication; fringe_m= Fringe Benefits; sup_m= Supervision; prom_m= Promotion; pay_m= Pay; subj_m= Subjective Social Status; orgC_m= Organisational Culture; pers_m= Personal Orientation; exp_m= Expectation

This refined model emphasizes the importance of leadership in fostering a culture that uses data effectively, supported by user competencies and organizational systems. Knowledge Management System (KMS) has direct links to Transformational Leadership (TL) according to standardized regression weight of 0.338.* The results show transformational leadership facilitates the establishment and development of vital knowledge management systems. Effective knowledge management systems (KMS) have been associated with transformational leadership, especially in educational contexts. Transformational leaders are crucial in establishing organizational culture because they promote trust, cooperation, and communication—all of which are necessary for effective knowledge management and sharing (Faizi & Emadi, 2019). According to Gruenert, & Whitaker (2015), transformational leadership plays a crucial role in creating systems that foster knowledge flow and organizational learning. Leader behavior focused on inspiration and vision creation is vital for developing knowledge management systems according to their findings.

Further, the influence of KMS on DU output reaches 0.588 according to the regression results (p-value 0.000). The implementation of efficient knowledge management systems makes possible the use of data for educational decision-making processes. The relationship between data utilization for decision-making and KMS exists as a validated concept throughout published literature. KMS adoption receives support through the development of corporate culture that enhances data utilization for decision-making (Ostroff et al., 2013). A well-designed KMS provides accurate and up-to-date information to leaders and educators allowing them to make informed decisions and

achieve data smooth transmission School leaders enhance the KMS-decision-making alignment by encouraging open information sharing.

Furthermore, analysis demonstrates a direct relationship between Data-Driven Decision Making (DDDM) transformation to Data Use (DU) since the regression weights measured at 0.132 maintain statistical significance (p-value.079). Even though the correlation is a little weaker, it still shows that using data improves the decision-making process as a whole. Particularly in educational institutions, data-driven decision-making (DDDM) has been identified as a critical component in enhancing organizational performance. Datnow, Park, and Wohlstetter (2021) claim that when instructors and school administrators use data effectively, choices are made based on real-time data rather than conjecture, which improves instructional methods. Mwamatandala and Muneja (2020) emphasized how DUPS helps teachers make better decisions by improving their capacity to modify their teaching methods in response to student data.

Moreover, the effectiveness of the knowledge management system has a large beneficial influence on data-driven decision-making processes, as evidenced by the direct effect from KMS to DDDM, which has a significant regression weight of 0.668 (p-value 0.000). The model fits the data well, as indicated by the RMSEA of 0.035. The model provides an excellent match to the data, as indicated by the CFI, TLI, and NFI scores. The conclusion that the best-fit model accurately depicts the relationships between the variables driving data-driven decision-making in schools is supported by these findings.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study are based on the results of the analyzed data which shows that the level of transformative leadership had overall mean of 3.83 described as high. The level of knowledge management system (KMS) got an overall mean score of 4.05 described as high. There are six domains for knowledge management system. Level of data use got an overall mean 3.73 described as high. standard deviation is less than 1 suggesting homogenous response from the research respondents. The data-driven decision-making (DDDM) got an overall 3.78 described as high. Also, the data-driven decision-making (DDDM) best-fit model suggested that transformative leadership and KMS are important factors in DDDM. The CMIN/df = 1.357, NFI = 0.912, TLI = 0.971, CFI = 0.975, GFI = 0.931, RMSEA = 0.035, and P-close = 0.991 are all excellent fit indices for the model. In addition, the best-fit model's indicators included important metrics for data utilization, KMS, and transformative leadership.

The study concludes that the school administrators demonstrate transformational leadership at a high level which denoted that their transformational leadership was often manifested. Knowledge Management System demonstrated high which means that knowledge management system among school leaders was oftentimes manifested. A high KMS rating demonstrates how the institution effectively gathered data and arranged it for enhanced decision-making processes. Data use of school leaders demonstrated high which means that their data use was oftentimes utilized. Data-informed procedures permeate the entire operational framework of the school on a daily basis. The data-driven decision-making of school leaders was described as high which indicated that their data-driven decision-making was often performed. The conclusion proved the vital role statistics play in supporting school reform projects.

Moreover, the effectiveness of data utilization in academic institutions was highly influenced by the collated impact of knowledge management systems and transformational leadership. The strong model fit statistics inferred that these two variables must operate in tandem to bolster data-driven decision-making of the school leaders aligned with the best-fit model. The structural relationship observed between data use, KMS, and transformational leadership emphasize the underlying role these factors play in enabling academic institutions to implement effective data-driven decision-making. The mutual influence of these variables denoted to a key factor in molding the school performance dynamics.

The findings highlight the need for the school leaders to have structured innovated programs, interdisciplinary collaboration forum, and mentoring initiatives be institutionalized to sustain and expand their intellectual engagement, the urgency that the schools introduce digital platforms for knowledge exchange such as KMS tool operation trainings, formalize documentation of best practices, and promote a culture of shared learning through regular peer-sharing sessions done by the school leaders and teachers, schools may create a program for standardized data management systems, training for advanced data analytics, including the use of data dashboards, predictive modeling, and ethical data interpretations and it is recommended that school administrators may establish data reform usage as the top priority and enhance implementation of data analysis for school improvements, school may adopt regular data review cycles – such as quarterly audits, progress monitoring, and goal-alignment sessions, to ensure that the data remains central to all strategic decisions.

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